

UNCHAINED R -SEQUENCES AND A GENERALIZED CASSINI FORMULA

George A. Hisert
Berkeley, California. USA
 gah454@yahoo.com

Received: 10/28/14, Revised: 8/11/15, Accepted: 9/19/15, Published: 10/13/15

Abstract

This paper posits a new method to analyze r -sequences without limitation as to type of number or the value of the seeds. That method is then used to derive identities applicable to all r -sequences, including a counterpart to Cassini's Formula. The paper also shows that any element in an r -sequence can be expressed as a linear function of r randomly chosen consecutive elements of the r -sequence using coefficients which are identical for all sequences of the same order.

1. Introduction

There have been many articles concerning sequences which satisfy the recurrence equation

$$G_{i+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} G_{i-j}^{(r)} \quad (1)$$

where r is an integer greater than 1, the term (r) is a superscript and not an exponent, and i and j are any integers (including negative integers in the case of i). If a subscript i is negative, the value of $G_i^{(r)}$ is determined by

$$G_i^{(r)} = G_{i+r}^{(r)} - \left(\sum_{j=1}^{r-1} G_{i+j}^{(r)} \right). \quad (2)$$

The seeds (the values of $G_i^{(r)}$ for $0 \leq i < r$) are often set at $G_0^{(r)} = 0, G_1^{(r)} = 1$ and $G_i^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} G_j^{(r)}$ for $1 < i < r$. For instance, if $r = 4$, then $G_{i+1}^{(4)} = G_i^{(4)} + G_{i-1}^{(4)} + G_{i-2}^{(4)} + G_{i-3}^{(4)}$ for $i > 3$ and frequently $G_0^{(4)} = 0, G_1^{(4)} = 1, G_2^{(4)} = 1$ and $G_3^{(4)} = 2$, yielding the sequence 0, 1, 1, 2, 4, 8, 15, 29, 56, 108, 208, 401, ... *However, much of the analysis which follows is independent of the value of the seeds.* For example, the analysis applies equally to the 4-sequence 2, 5, 7, 14, 28, 54, 103, 199, ...

and to the 4-sequence with seeds $\sqrt{13}, -2.9, \pi$ and $\tan^{-1}(2)$. The analysis also applies regardless of whether the numbers in the sequence are positive or negative, rational or irrational, real or imaginary. As suggested in [6], it may be worthwhile to be spreading our nets more widely. The present article is the outgrowth of several prior articles covering broad results for uniform power identities [2, 3].

For $r = 3$ and 4, these sequences have been referred to as tribonacci and tetranacci sequences. Instead, we use the language of [5] and refer to sequences which fulfill the condition in (1) as *r-sequences* or *sequences of order r*, notwithstanding that our definition of the term is significantly broader than that used in [5].

2. A Preliminary Model: $r = 5$

Solely for the purpose of introducing certain concepts and terminology, we let $r = 5$, pick n randomly and look for certain patterns in sequences of order 5. For greater ease in discovering patterns, we set $v = G_{n+4}^{(5)}, w = G_{n+3}^{(5)}, x = G_{n+2}^{(5)}, y = G_{n+1}^{(5)}$ and $z = G_n^{(5)}$ and then expand for nearby values of $G_{n+s}^{(5)}$. As s increases, we calculate $G_{n+s}^{(5)}$ by repeated use of equation (1). For values of $G_j^{(5)}$ where $j < n$, we calculate $G_j^{(5)} = G_{j+5}^{(5)} - G_{j+4}^{(5)} - G_{j+3}^{(5)} - G_{j+2}^{(5)} - G_{j+1}^{(5)}$. Putting the results in tabular form, we obtain Table 1. We also tentatively define a related *r*-sequence $L_m^{(5)} = G_m^{(5)} + G_{m-1}^{(5)}$

s	$G_{n+s}^{(5)}$	$G_{n-s}^{(5)}$
0	z	$-$
1	y	$v - w - x - y - z$
2	x	$-v + 2w$
3	w	$- w + 2x$
4	v	$-x + 2y$
5	$v + w + x + y + z$	$-y + 2z$
6	$2v + 2w + 2x + 2y + z$	$2v - 2w - 2x - 2y - 3z$
7	$4v + 4w + 4x + 3y + 2z$	$-3v + 5w + x + y + z$
8	$8v + 8w + 7x + 6y + 4z$	$v - 4w + 4x$
9	$16v + 15w + 14x + 12y + 8z$	$w - 4x + 4y$
10	$31v + 30w + 28x + 24y + 16z$	$x - 4y + 4z$
11	$61v + 59w + 55x + 47y + 31z$	$4v - 4w - 4x - 3y - 8z$
12	$120v + 116w + 108x + 92y + 61z$	$-8v + 12w + 4x + 4y + 5z$

Table 1: r = 5

as the Lucasian counterpart to $G_m^{(5)}$. A similar table can be easily prepared for $L_m^{(5)}$. But for now we will be focusing on identities in which only $L_{n+1}^{(5)}$ appears from the

sequence L . In the case of a 5-sequence, $L_{n+1}^{(5)} = y + z$.

Looking at Table 1, one can see certain identities without the need to solve a set of simultaneous linear equations. We note that $G_{n-5}^{(5)} = 2z - y$. Hence we have the *shift formula* catalogued as Theorem 1 in [1]:

$$G_{n+1}^{(5)} = 2G_n^{(5)} - G_{n-5}^{(5)}. \tag{3}$$

One also notes that $3y^2 + 6z^2 - (2z - y)^2 = 2y^2 + 4yz + 2z^2 = 2(y + z)^2$ or

$$3(G_{n+1}^{(5)})^2 + 6(G_n^{(5)})^2 - (G_{n-5}^{(5)})^2 = 2(L_{n+1}^{(5)})^2. \tag{4}$$

Likewise taking $G_{n+5}^{(5)}$ and $G_{n-1}^{(5)}$ and setting $A = w + x + y + z$, one sees that

$$\begin{aligned} G_{n+5}^{(5)2} - G_{n-1}^{(5)2} &= (v + A)^2 - (v - A)^2 \\ &= 4Av \\ &= 4Av + 4v^2 - 4v^2 \\ &= 4[v^2 + vw + vx + vy + vz] - 4v^2 \\ &= 4v[(v + w + x + y + z) - v] \\ &= 4G_{n+4}^{(5)}(G_{n+5}^{(5)} - G_{n+4}^{(5)}). \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Similarly, taking $G_{n+6}^{(5)}$ and $G_{n-6}^{(5)}$, one obtains the identity

$$G_{n+6}^{(5)2} - G_{n-6}^{(5)2} = 8(G_{n+5}^{(5)} - G_{n+4}^{(5)})(2G_{n+4}^{(5)} - G_n^{(5)}). \tag{6}$$

Not only does the above method dispense with solving simultaneous equations in deriving identities, but it also provides a more transparent view of the relationship among numbers in a sequence.

3. All $r > 1$

We now generalize for all integers $r > 1$. For any integer $r > 1$, we set r variables to equal $G_n^{(r)}$ and the numbers in the sequence immediately after $G_n^{(r)}$. We label the variables v_0 to v_{r-1} . We then let $v_i = G_{n+i}^{(r)}$ and construct Table 2 by letting $A = G_{i+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} G_{i-j}^{(r)}$. Then $G_{i+2}^{(r)} = G_{i+1}^{(r)} + A - G_{i-r}^{(r)} = 2A - G_{i-r}^{(r)}$, etc. For negative i , we apply equation (2) by iteration.

Table 2 can be extended indefinitely. Using the same techniques used in the prior section, one can readily derive the following identities which hold true for any

s	$G_{n+s}^{(r)}$	$G_{n-s}^{(r)}$
0	v_0	—
1	v_1	$v_{r-1} - \sum_{j=0}^{r-2} v_j$
2	v_2	$2v_{r-2} - v_{r-1}$
3	v_3	$2v_{r-3} - v_{r-2}$
4	v_4	$2v_{r-4} - v_{r-3}$
.
r-1	v_{r-1}	$2v_1 - v_2$
r	$\sum_{j=0}^{r-1} v_j$	$2v_0 - v_1$
r+1	$2(\sum_{j=1}^{r-1} v_j) + v_0$	$2v_{r-1} - \sum_{j=1}^{r-2} v_j - 3v_0$
r+2	$4(\sum_{j=2}^k v_j) + 3v_1 + 2v_0$	$-3v_{r-1} + 5v_{r-2} + \sum_{j=0}^{r-3} v_j$
r+3	$8(\sum_{j=3}^k v_j) + 7v_2 + 6v_1 + 4v_0$	$v_{r-1} - 4v_{r-2} + 4v_{r-3}$
r+4	$16(\sum_{j=4}^k v_j) + 15v_2 + 14v_2 + 12v_1 + 8v_0$	$v_{r-2} - 4v_{r-3} + 4v_{r-4}$
r+4	add prior r entries above	$v_{r-3} - 4v_{r-4} + 4v_{r-5}$
r+5	add prior r entries above	$v_{r-4} - 4v_{r-5} + 4v_{r-6}$
r+6	add prior r entries above	$v_{r-5} - 4v_{r-6} + 4v_{r-7}$

Table 2: A neighborhood for general r

r-sequence where $r \geq 2$.

$$3G_{n+1}^{(r)2} + 6G_n^{(r)2} - G_{n-r}^{(r)2} = 2L_{n+1}^{(r)2}, \tag{7}$$

$$G_{n+r}^{(r)2} - G_{n-1}^{(r)2} = 4G_{n+r-1}^{(r)}(G_{n+r}^{(r)} - G_{n+r-1}^{(r)}), \tag{8}$$

$$G_{n+(r+1)}^{(r)2} - G_{n-(r+1)}^{(r)2} = 8(G_{n+r}^{(r)} - G_{n+r-1}^{(r)})(2G_{n+r-1}^{(r)} - G_n^{(r)}). \tag{9}$$

One can readily derive other identities which hold true for all r-sequences.

4. Cassini’s Formula

A review of Table 2 suggests a general counterpart to Cassini’s formula.

Theorem 1. For any r-sequence $G^{(r)}$ where r, m and n are integers and $n = m - (r + 1)$,

$$G_m^{(r)2} - G_{m+1}^{(r)}G_{m-1}^{(r)} = G_n^{(r)2} - G_{n+r}^{(r)}G_{n-r}^{(r)}. \tag{10}$$

Proof. If we let $A = \sum_{j=2}^{r-1} v_j$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_m^{(r)2} - G_{m+1}^{(r)}G_{m-1}^{(r)} &= [2A + (2v_1 + v_0)]^2 - [A + (v_1 + v_0)][4A + (3v_1 + 2v_0)] \\
 &= 4A^2 + 4A(2v_1 + v_0) + (2v_1 + v_0)^2 \\
 &\quad - [4A^2 + A(7v_1 + 6v_0) + (v_1 + v_0)(3v_1 + 2v_0)] \\
 &= A(v_1 - 2v_0) + [(v_1)^2 - (v_1)(v_0) - (v_0)^2] \\
 &= A(v_1 - 2v_0) + [(v_1 + v_0)(v_1 - 2v_0)] + (v_0)^2 \\
 &= (A + v_1 + v_0)(v_1 - 2v_0) + (v_0)^2 \\
 &= (v_0)^2 - [(2v_0 - v_1)(\sum_{j=0}^{r-1} v_j)] \\
 &= (G_n^{(r)})^2 - G_{n-r}^{(r)}G_{n+r}^{(r)}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

□

This generalized version of Cassini’s formula holds for all values of $r > 1$ without regard to the values of the seeds. For $r = 2$ and the traditional Fibonacci sequence, Theorem 1 gives the traditional Cassini Formulae $F_m^2 - F_{m+1}F_{m-1} = (-1)^{m+1}$ and $F_n^2 - F_{n+2}F_{n-2} = (-1)^n$. In addition, if $r = 2$ and the seeds of the traditional Fibonacci sequence are varied so that $F_0 = A$ and $F_1 = B$, then Theorem 1 yields $G_n^{(2)2} - G_{n+1}^{(2)}G_{n-1}^{(2)} = (B^2 - A^2 - AB)(-1)^{n+1}$.

It is stated in [7] that the identity $L_n^2 - 5F_n^2 = 4(-1)^n$ is a fundamental ingredient in many 2-sequence identities. But that identity is a mere reformulation of Cassini’s formula.

$$\begin{aligned}
 4(-1)^n &= L_n^2 - 5F_n^2 \\
 &= (F_{n+1} + F_{n-1})^2 - 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} + 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} - 5F_n^2 \\
 &= [F_{n+1}^2 + 2F_{n+1}F_{n-1} + F_{n-1}^2 - 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1}] + 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} - 5F_n^2 \\
 &= (F_{n+1} - F_{n-1})^2 + 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} - 5F_n^2 \\
 &= F_n^2 + 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} - 5F_n^2 \\
 &= 4F_{n+1}F_{n-1} - 4F_n^2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

It may be that (10) plays a similar role when $r > 2$. See [4] for the author’s use of Cassini’s formula in non-uniform power identities.

5. Primary r -Sequences

Returning to Table 1, one notes that the coefficients of v form a 5-sequence. The same holds for each of w, x, y and z . In tabular form, they are set forth in Table

3. For ease of reference, we will temporarily call these sequences $(V), (W), (X), (Y)$ and (Z) with subscripts to coincide with the value of s at the top of Table 3. For example, $x_8 = 7$.

s	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
V	2	0	0	0	-1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	4	8	16	31
W	-2	0	0	-1	2	-1	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	4	8	15	30
X	-2	0	-1	2	0	-1	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	4	7	14	28
Y	-2	-1	2	0	0	-1	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	3	6	12	24
Z	-3	2	0	0	0	-1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	4	8	16

Table 3: Primary Sequences for $r = 5$

Note that

(1) (V) and (Z) are the basic 5-sequence (as presented in [5]) shifted respectively one and two notches up;

(2) $y_n = z_n + z_{n-1}, x_n = z_n + y_{n-1}, w_n = z_n + x_{n-1}$ and $v_n = z_n + w_{n-1}$; and

(3) the relationships in (2) can be joined together to yield

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_n &= z_n + z_{n-1} \\
 x_n &= z_n + z_{n-1} + z_{n-2} \\
 w_n &= z_n + z_{n-1} + z_{n-2} + z_{n-3} \\
 v_n &= z_n + z_{n-1} + z_{n-2} + z_{n-3} + z_{n-4} \\
 &= z_{n+1}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{13}$$

We dub these sequences as the *primary sequences of order 5* and then distinguish them from one another (in the order Z, Y, X, W and V) as the *first, second, etc* primary sequence of order 5. The sequences will be represented by $P_i^{(5)}$ for $i = 1$ to r . The individual numbers in the sequences will be symbolized by $p_{i,j}^{(5)}$ for the j -th number in sequence $P_i^{(5)}$.

This table can be expanded to any $r > 1$. Instead of arranging the primary sequences horizontally as in Table 3, we arrange them vertically on a new Table 4, with the first primary sequence $P_1^{(r)}$ on the right. To save space, we exclude the easy cases of $r < 5$. For ease of reference, we break the table into three segments. In the middle segment, we arbitrarily choose the seed $p_{i,0}^{(r)}$ to be that row in which $p_{1,0}^{(r)} = 1$ and $p_{i,0}^{(r)} = 0$ for $1 < i \leq r$.

$P_{i,j}^{(r)}$	$i = r$	$r - 1$	$r - 2$	6	5	4	3	2	1
j =											
$r + 4$	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	15	14	12	8
$r + 3$	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	7	6	4
$r + 2$	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	2
$r + 1$	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
r	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$r - 1$	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$r - 2$	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$r - 3$	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
...
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
-1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
-2	-1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-3	0	0	0	-1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
-4	0	0	-1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
...
$-r + 2$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	2	0	0
$-r + 1$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	2	0
$-r$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	2
$-r - 1$	2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-3
$-r - 2$	-3	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$-r - 3$	1	-4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$-r - 4$	0	1	-4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4: Primary Sequences for $r > 4$

In the first segment of the table, we set forth the coefficients of the identity $G_k^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} (p_{j,k}^{(r)} G_j^{(r)})$ where $k > r - 1$, based on the following iterative process. Let $A = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} G_{i-j}^{(r)}$. Then $G_r^{(r)} = A, G_{r+1}^{(r)} = G_r^{(r)} + A - G_0^{(r)} = 2A - G_0^{(r)}$; $G_{r+2}^{(r)} = G_{r+1}^{(r)} + G_r^{(r)} + A - G_1^{(r)} - G_0^{(r)} = 4A - G_1^{(r)} - 2G_0^{(r)}$; etc. The entries for $r + k$ where $k < r$ are either $2^k - 2^{k-i}$ or $2^k - 2^{k-i} - 1$. The third segment of the Table A displays the values of the sequences as the subscripts move into negative territory, using equation (2) by iteration.

One can now easily posit the following theorem:

Theorem 2. For any numbers $G_m^{(r)}$ and $G_n^{(r)}$ which are part of an r -sequence $G_{i+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} G_{i-j}^{(r)}$ where r, m, n, q, j and i are integers and $r > 1$, there exists r

primary r -sequences $p_{q,k}^{(r)}$ (being the k -th number in the q -th primary r -sequence) such that $G_m^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} [(p_{j+1,m}^{(r)})(G_{n+j}^{(r)})]$.

Proof. The proof follows from the definition of the primary sequences. □

Other findings include:

- (1) $p_{2,j}^{(r)} = [p_{1,j}^{(r)} + p_{1,j-1}^{(r)}]$ and, for $2 < i \leq r$, $p_{i,j}^{(r)} = [p_{1,j}^{(r)} + p_{i-1,j-1}^{(r)}]$, and
- (2) for $1 < i \leq r$, $p_{i,j}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} [p_{1,i-j}^{(r)}]$, and
- (3) the values of $p_{i,j}^{(r)}$ for $1 \leq i \leq r$ and $j > r$ can be expressed as a linear function of powers of 2.

All of these results can be proved using simple induction. I leave to the reader the derivation of the function referred to in clause (3) of the immediately preceding paragraph.

Most importantly, the primary sequences for any r -sequence are identical to that of any other sequence of the same order, regardless of the seeds of the r -sequence and regardless of whether the numbers of the r -sequence are positive or negative, rational or irrational, real or imaginary. Hence, in many cases, analysis of an r -sequence can be reduced to an analysis of the primary r -sequences. For instance, if one extends Table 4 upward, by just looking at Table 4, the possibility of the identity

$$G_{n+2}^{(r)} - 4G_{n+1}^{(r)} + 4G_n^{(r)} = G_{n-2r}^{(r)} \tag{14}$$

pops out. As indicated in [7], the derivation of an identity is often more difficult than the proof of the identity. The structure set forth in this paper makes the derivation considerably easier for a large number of identities.

6. Topics for Future Study

As indicated in [5], much further work needs to be done. Some issues are suggested in [5]. Still additional issues are raised by this paper. For example, [5] expresses a view as to the counterpart to the Lucas sequence for r -sequences. The author of this article believes that there are better candidates, based in part on the results set forth above. The author hopes to address that issue in a separate paper.

In addition, the author solicits the input of readers on the following conjectures:

- 1. In order that an r -sequence as defined solely by (1) be *seed neutral* (that is, the sequence applies regardless of the *seeds*), the spread of the identity (the difference

between the highest and lowest subscripts in the identity) must be at least r , the order of the sequence.

2. For any integers r and s where $r > 2$ and $0 < s < r$

$$\sum_{j=0}^s 2^j (-1)^{(s-j)} \binom{s}{j} G_{s-j}^{(r)} = G_{n-sr}^{(r)}. \quad (15)$$

Acknowledgements The author wishes to thank the editor of Integers for his patience and assistance to the author in making the transition from publishing on legal matters to publishing on mathematical topics.

References

- [1] H. Gabai, *Generalized Fibonacci k-sequences*, Fibonacci Quart. **8** (1970), 31-38.
- [2] G.A. Hisert, *A different method for deriving Fibonacci power identities*, JP J. Algebra, Number Theory and Appl. **24** (2012), 1-26.
- [3] G.A. Hisert, *Further results on deriving Fibonacci uniform power identities*, JP J. Algebra, Number Theory and Appl. **28** (2013), 13-43.
- [4] G.A. Hisert, *Application of the dual polynomial method to Fibonacci non-uniform power identities*, JP J. of Algebra, Number Theory and Appl. **31** (2013), 39-50.
- [5] F.T.Howard and C.Cooper, *Some identities for r-Fibonacci numbers*, Fibonacci Quart. **49** (2011), 231 - 242 .
- [6] D. Kalman and R. Mena, *The Fibonacci numbers - exposed*, Math. Mag. **76** (2003), 167-181.
- [7] S. Rabinowitz, *Algorithmic manipulation of Fibonacci identities*, Proc. 6th Conference of Fibonacci Numbers and Their Applications (1996), 389-408.